

THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya. Raqamlashtirishning paydo bo'lishi an'anaviy bozor tuzilmalarining chuqur o'zgarishini ta'minladi. Avtomatlashtirish va texnologiyalar integratsiyasi ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatish segmentlarining keng doirasiga, shu jumladan turizm sanoatida keng tarqaldi. Raqamlashtirish darajasi har doim o'sib bormoqda va besh yildan keyin turizm sohasi tanib bo'lmas holga kelishiga ishonish uchun asoslar bor. Turistlarning xohish-istaklari, qolaversa, millati, dini, oila a'zolarining sonidan kelib chiqib, sayyohlarning maqsadiga qarab, sun'iy intellekt ularga shaxsiylashtirilgan tavsiyalar beradi, shu jumladan, diqqatga sazovor joylar va tegishli qo'llanmalar bilan VR va AR kabi aloqalar o'rnatishga yordam beradi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida turizm sohasida yangi raqamli platformalar va ekotizimlarning yaratilishi mamlakatning mavjud turizm salohiyatini jahon miqyosida targ'ib qilishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Sayyohlarga ko'proq foyda keltirishi uchun yangi texnologiyalarni joriy etish va yuqori saviyali kadrlarni tayyorlash muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: rivojlanish, kelajak, sun'iy intellekt, raqamli, innovatsiyalar, hamkorlik.

Аннотация. Наступление цифровизации ускорило глубокую трансформацию традиционных рыночных структур. Интеграция автоматизации и технологий стала всепроникающей в широкий спектр сегментов рынка, включая туристическую индустрию. Степень цифровизации постоянно растет, и есть основания полагать, что через пять лет отрасль будет неузнаваема. В зависимости от страны проживания туристов, национальности, вероисповедания, количества членов семьи, исходя из цели поездки туристов, искусственный интеллект предоставляет им персонализированные рекомендации, включая программу осмотра достопримечательностей и контакты подходящих гидов. Создание новых цифровых платформ и экосистем в сфере туризма в Республике Узбекистан будет способствовать продвижению существующего туристического потенциала страны на мировом уровне. Важно внедрять новые технологии и готовить высококвалифицированные кадры, чтобы приносить больше пользы туристам.

Ключевые слова: развитие, будущее, искусственный интеллект, цифровые технологии, инновации, партнерства.

Abstract. The advent of digitalization has precipitated a profound transformation of traditional market structures. The integration of automation and technology has become pervasive across a vast array of market segments, including the tourism industry. The degree of digitalization is increasing all the time, and there is reason to believe that in five years the industry will be unrecognizable.

Depends on tourists' home country, nationality, religion, number of family members, based on the purpose of the tourists' trip, artificial intelligence provides them with personalized

recommendations, including a program of sightseeing and contacts of suitable guides. The creation of new digital platforms and ecosystems in the realm of tourism within the Republic of Uzbekistan will help promote the existing tourism potential of the country at the global level. It is important to introduce new technologies and train high-level personnel in order to bring more benefits to tourists.

Key words: *development, future, artificial intelligence, digital, innovation, partnerships.*

Starting to manage tourism business using digital platform and technology may cause costs and risks at first, but with a long-term plan, it is proven to pay off in the case of developed countries. In this regard, the successful transition of tourism industry enterprises into the digital economy hinges on a comprehensive digital transformation and integration strategy that engages system integrators of new technologies.

One of the primary challenges inherent to the digitalization of the digital economy pertains to the necessity for integrating the disparate platforms utilized by disparate developers into a unified network¹. The platform is a single digital platform for all entities in tourism area is calculated and covers several solutions at the same time.

- It is incumbent upon the parties to the transaction, the seller and the buyer, to conclude the transaction and to evaluate the reliability of their respective transaction partners;

- seller engages in collaborative endeavors with other market participants to identify potential partnerships and jointly create value.

The most promising avenue for addressing this issue is the creation of a digital ecosystem centered on an autonomous infrastructure platform. This platform would assume a pivotal role in facilitating the functioning of the ecosystem, as detailed in the following section:

- the creation of a single area of cooperation will lead to the creation of unity between tourist entities and digital platforms, which, in turn, causes the provision of security and satisfaction of needs;

- the use of applications, websites and technological facilities in the process of providing services to tourists greatly contributes to the development of the sector.

Conversely, platformization affords stakeholders in the tourism industry considerable competitive advantages:

- the value of industry platforms is enhanced by "network effects," which increase as the number of users expands;

- it is commonly acknowledged that digital transformation of enterprises entails certain costs, which are assumed by the relevant platforms. In return for the provision of their services, these platforms benefit from the transformation process;

- the creation of the proposed new business model encourages the reduction of unhealthy competition between participants and, on the contrary, mutually beneficial cooperation.

The Uzbekistan government's decision to extend the state program on digital transformation of the country's industries until 2030 is indicative of its acknowledgment of

¹ Lopez-Cordova E. Digital Platforms and the Demand for International Tourism Services. The World Bank, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-9147>.

the pivotal role that digital transformation contributes to the growth and development of the national economy. One of the program's components is the scientific and practical elaboration and regulatory support of this direction of development in various economic sectors.

In consequence of international experience and recommendations, we are in a position to present a number of different digital platforms.

The discrete software products Java, iOS, Android, Bitrix, and others serve as the foundation for a number of instrumental digital platforms.

- Predix is an infrastructural digital platform based on the ecosystem of Public Services and CoBrain Analytics, which consists of digital transformation market participants.

A platform comprising digital and mobile applications affords users the opportunity to engage in transactional exchange within a unified information environment. Examples of such platforms include Booking.com, Airbnb, and Uber.

Analyst agency International Data Corporation (IDC)² noted that travel companies will spend \$2,3 trillion per year on digital transformation between 2020 and 2024, with global investment in digital transformation technologies expected to reach at least \$7,4 trillion over the same time period.

They also offered the following predictions for digital transformation:

First, the use of digital platforms and the advancement of ecosystems. By 2025, due to global market volatility, 75% of companies, particularly in tourism will use digital platforms and ecosystems to adapt business strategies to new markets, industries, ecosystems.

Second, 30% of tourism organizations must accelerate innovation to change business models, while shortening the timeline of transformation programs for the sake of concrete results.

Third, by 2023, most companies will accept the importance of combining digital transformation strategy with resource efficiency.

Fourth, the process of company adaptation in the digital economy over the next five years will be characterized by the formation of a corporate culture optimized for digital transformation among half of the travel companies. This culture will be customer-centric and will utilize big data.

Fifth, 60% of Global 2000 companies will create their own business transformation platforms to support innovation and growth in the new digital environment³.

With so many digital technology options available, it is challenging to identify and select which ones will specifically benefit your company. Travel companies should conduct thorough quantitative and qualitative research before investing in any digital solution.

Quantitative research using business intelligence tools collects data that tracks performance, experience, or engagement, which can then back up qualitative observations.

One way to do things effectively is that both long-term and short-term digital plans must be elaborated upon and expanded upon in order to achieve the desired outcome to address immediate and future needs. The short-term plan should be for about three to six months, while the long-term

² International Data Corporation (IDC) DC is a leading provider of information and consulting services, and organizer of events in the information technology, telecommunications and consumer technology markets. IDC is a leading provider of information and consulting services, and organizer of events in the information technology, telecommunications and consumer technology markets.

³ The total market capitalization of the 2,000 companies included in the list grew by 47% over the year, to \$79,8 trillion, notes American Forbes. The companies' combined revenues fell 6% to \$39,8 trillion, and their profits fell 24% to \$2,5 trillion. The value of company assets increased by 11%, to \$223 trillion. The minimum market value required for inclusion in the rating was \$8,26 billion this year, down from \$5,27 billion last year.

plan should be for about six to twelve months. To get an accurate picture of the productivity of the travel company, regular performance tests of their relationship systems should be conducted. Employees may also be surveyed to determine how they respond to technology.

It is critical that travel companies develop a holistic plan for the database, taking into account potential privacy issues or managing a growing amount of data. Often companies do not understand how to maximize the value of the data they have. To do this, they should conduct a thorough audit of their existing database. This will sort out what digital technologies are currently being used effectively and what the experts' opinions are on this. This can facilitate the discovery of the data that your business possesses, the methods by which it may be utilized, and the additional resources that may prove beneficial.

The tourism industry possesses a number of characteristics that serve to determine the efficacy of the selection of digital technologies as a tool for digital transformation within this sector:

1. High importance of providing services to tourists and intangible goods;
2. Lack of offers for tourists in the tourism market;
3. Tourists attach special importance to the company's reputation and brand when making a decision;
4. It should be taken into account the presence of various companies in the tourist market;
5. In light of erratic consumer demand and the inherent volatility of seasonal patterns, companies in the industry are compelled to pursue a strategy of specialization, forming alliances and partnerships with other organizations in order to differentiate their service offerings (transport, excursions, agency, etc.) and thereby mitigate the financial burden associated with production costs.
6. Consequently, a distinct tourist product is typically constituted by a collection of discrete economic activities.

These factors collectively indicate a high level of interaction between economic entities within the tourism sector, which a digital platform is well-positioned to facilitate.

It is of great importance to develop a strategic plan to reinforce the involvement of tourism organizations in the digital transformation process of the sustainable development of the tourism industry. The digital transformation process has the advantage of websites and mobile applications, which facilitate the rapid and effective exchange of information, reduce the costs of interactions, enhance labour productivity and eliminate the necessity for costly intermediaries. In countries where tourism is well developed, a variety of strategies have been implemented.

As our research has shown, the introduction of travel platforms will lead to a recovery and increase in the profitability of travel companies of travel service providers. As reported by the Statistical Committee, the number of tourists from abroad visiting Uzbekistan increased from 7 million in 2023 to 5,2 million in 2022 and 3,4 million in 2021. This represents a significant growth of over 4,8 times⁴ the previous year's figures.

It is of significant importance to acknowledge that the implementation of all the directions on a single platform is an inefficient approach, as it presents challenges in organizing and utilizing the platform system. In light of these considerations, the optimal strategy would be to provide an ecosystem of platforms, with the capacity to interconnect disparate information flows and share a unified information repository available to all relevant digital platforms (platform offers clients the ability to make online bookings and to select their desired travel destination).

⁴ Travel and Tourism, 2023

<https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/uzbekistan-travel-and-tourism>

The digital infrastructure platform in the form of an ecosystem is directly proportional to the appearance and quality of tourism services and information provision, as well as the number of participants in the tourism market, in terms of reliability, efficiency and satisfaction of tourists' needs.

There are a number of important requirements for the development of the tourism ecosystem:⁵

1. In tourism, all available information is considered as "new oil", regardless of its size, platforms have a great role in order to quickly collect, process and analyze it⁶.

2. Subsequently, the findings of the study, comprising statistical and dynamic research, are transformed into competencies, models and rules. In addition, there is a need to institutionalize relations between participants and clarify their activities⁷.

3. Participants in the tourism market should be studied separately in order to guarantee the comprehensiveness and expansion of relations.

4. The division of responsibilities among all participants of digital platforms serves to increase the level of specialization.

5. Security of travelers' information and money transfers is guaranteed.

6. In order for the digital platform to be profitable, it is necessary to have the right of choice of the participants and create a healthy competition. This enables participants to combine and integrate their own or other digital solutions (e.g., the integration of booking.com and ozon travel⁸) into the platform via API (application programming interface).

The above represents the ideal of digital relationships in tourism; however, there is another aspect to consider. The main problem in the implementation of these principles and criteria is the human factor, in particular, the stubbornness of thoughts and actions shown by some managers and employees of the tourism company.

Despite the high importance of digital solutions and platforms, management in tourism depends on the creativity of the human factor, the level of all employees. Such factors must be considered in any assessment and supported by legislation in the implementation of the regional (national) infrastructure digital platform strategy, taking into account the country's specific characteristics and level of digital development. First and foremost, guaranteeing the security of interactions and relationships between all participants participating in the platform is the highest goal to be implemented.

The long-term strategy for the digitization of tourism in our country allows to increase the efficiency of all existing processes at a high speed, attract innovations, and earn more money for tourism service providers.

⁵ Lindroos N. The digital transformation of a ski resort: a case study. thesis, master of science. AALTO University School of science, 2017.

⁶ Data aggregation is the process of collecting all your data together. Many organizations collect data from multiple sources with the goal of eventually combining these different data sets. When aggregating data, organizations carefully choose where their data sets come from so that they can later gain insights from a consolidated version of that data. The quality of the final data analysis depends on the accuracy and thoroughness of data aggregation.

⁷ Dynamic research is the sequential collection of feedback from the same group of people over a long period of time. Dynamic research can do the following: track changes in people's opinions and experiences identify problems early to prevent negative outcomes

⁸ «Создание своего отельного продукта, поддержка и интеграция с поставщиками – достаточно затратный процесс. Скорее всего, у Ozon.travel было недостаточно объемов, которые сделали бы это направление прибыльным. Сотрудничество с Booking.com позволит сервису дополнительно зарабатывать и при этом ничего не тратить

Conclusion. Despite all kinds of positive and negative scenarios, the advent of digital transformation offers promising opportunities for the growth of tourism. The following activities can be proposed:

1. Wide use of digital tourism technologies in the framework of tourism education, visual study of historical areas, communication with speakers of other languages through rapid translation technologies. In areas with high tourist potential, it would be reasonable to suggest that introduce the use of multimedia technologies and guide applications.

2. The creation of mobile applications that reflect the amenities of tourist destinations for persons with limited opportunities and disabilities will be a great impetus in the development of barrier-free tourism. In light of the circumstances, it would seem reasonable to conclude that organize short-term training courses in the domain of tourism for disabled citizens of our republic and provide them with work (sign language-interpreters, guide services). It is appropriate to make virtual trips a full substitute for real travel for people with disabilities, as well as low-income citizens.

3. The creation of new digital platforms and ecosystems in the realm of tourism within the Republic of Uzbekistan will help promote the existing tourism potential of the country at the global level. It is important to introduce new technologies and train high-level personnel in order to bring more benefits to tourists.

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